

SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT "ENTREPRENEURSHIP"

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Annotation In the period of global development, the formation of legal knowledge and skills of entrepreneurs, the formation of their legal culture, the philosophical essence of such concepts as "entrepreneur", "innovator", "entrepreneur", "legal culture of an entrepreneur" are highlighted.

Key words: entrepreneurs, legal knowledge and skills, legal culture, "entrepreneur", "innovator", "entrepreneur", "legal culture of an entrepreneur", functional tasks, economic activity.

In the era of global development, the indicators of legal culture of entrepreneurs play an important role in the formation of legal knowledge and skills. The legal culture within the professional culture of an entrepreneur develops in the interrelationship of the system of knowing-understanding-implementing the legislation of the field. If we see that concepts such as "entrepreneur", "innovator", "entrepreneurial person", "legal culture of an entrepreneurial person" have an economic basis first of all, we have no doubt that this is a social phenomenon when we do a deeper analysis. Entrepreneurial activity, as well as the subjects of innovative-intellectual activity, are manifested in their functional tasks in the formation of the social and legal state, as well as their direct and indirect needs. By widely involving our citizens in intellectual activity and innovative entrepreneurial activities in modern society, we will achieve not only economic activity, but also social stability in them.

As a result of the reforms aimed at further liberalization and modernization of the economy in the new stage of development, there is a need to fight against monopolies, find the composition of modern forms of entrepreneurship, and develop a new system of their legal regulation. The participation of state bodies and the general public in the implementation of reforms in this direction is considered a liberal-democratic indicator. It also requires regular modernization of the production sector, for which the subjects of business activity are obliged to create the necessary conditions.

When answering questions about entrepreneurship, it would be more correct to start by emphasizing that entrepreneurship is one of the most important qualities inherent in the nature of our people.

"An entrepreneur is a master of his work, a dexterous, resourceful person, a business person. According to the saying of our people, such a person knows

the essence of work, can overcome the obstacles that stand in the way of his work, is aware of the results of mental work and getting a lot of profit" [1]. Based on the content of the qualities mentioned above, an "entrepreneurial person" is an individual who risks his activity and works on the basis of risk. Risk-taking requires a combination of the following qualities: bravery, generosity, generosity, kindness. It should be noted that from the very beginning, businessmen and traders, i.e. today's businessmen, have always been respected by the members of our society, they were seen as representatives of the respected community, and in folklore they were shown as role models for young people, i.e. artistic images such as businessmen, active and open-handed people we can observe. To this issue, the opinion of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev that "it is necessary to improve the education system aimed at forming the necessary skills for entrepreneurship in the population, it is necessary to involve international organizations, non-governmental non-profit organizations and non-governmental educational organizations in this process" [2] as a methodological solution to this issue possible.

An entrepreneur was the main criterion of a fair country's management, during the historical stages when the principles of entrepreneurship and creativity were supported, and the principles of entrepreneurship and creativity were supported. , there is information that such persons were rewarded and respected according to their work. "Entrepreneurship and accompanying forms of activity and economic categories were considered together with the individual. An entrepreneur has always been a separate person, and the attitude to money, property and trade, according to thinkers, depended on the qualities of this person" [3], shows that we can see the concepts of entrepreneurship and entrepreneur as complementary, indexical concepts.

For example, the vital confirmation of this idea can be found in the historical periods ruled by the Timurid dynasty. As our great-grandfather Amir Temur said: "A businessman, a man of courage and courage, a determined, enterprising and alert person is better than thousands of inactive and indifferent people" [4] and emphasizing the need to follow four rules in the management of the state, they are: consultation, consultation and consultation. It emphasizes solving problems, making firm decisions, business acumen, vigilance and prudence.

Therefore, "Amir Temur himself was first of all an entrepreneur, he well understood the expediency of carrying out entrepreneurship in harmony with decisiveness and vigilance in conducting state affairs, he lived with creative ideas and freed and improved the motherland inherited from his fathers by the spirit of his compatriots, compatriots and ancestors. considered it a sacred duty" [5]. Therefore, the concept of an entrepreneur is one of the social phenomena formed historically, it has been named differently in foreign times, and according to its essence, it mainly expresses a single meaning, that is, a businessman (entrepreneur), an entrepreneur who is a master of his work, is considered an innovator in the modern interpretation.

An entrepreneur is also an intelligent person who reacts to social reality, who is quick to pay attention not only to the lack of some product or labor force in terms of market relations, but also to their excess.

What about entrepreneurship? "Entrepreneurial activity is the activity of people taking risks and taking initiative within the framework of legislation on the basis of property responsibility. This activity is focused on achieving the intended goal - profit or business income - through the rational use of capital and resources. Market economy is an economy based on free enterprise, entrepreneurship. Therefore, for the formation and development of entrepreneurship, market relations should prevail in the economy. In other words, freedom in economic activity is required for the development of entrepreneurship" [6].

Due to the above-mentioned reasons and reasons, the development of free entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship, based on market relations and property rights, is being given great importance in the new Uzbekistan, and laws and decisions are being adopted to support entrepreneurship, which is an important link of the established class of owners, in every way. These legal documents adopted in the following years were an organic and logical continuation of a number of articles in the newly revised Constitution, which is our main law. In particular, in Article 41: "Each person has the right to be an owner..." [7], in addition, in Articles 66 and 68, there are norms related to entrepreneurship.

It follows that a number of freedoms are necessary for the formation and wide spread of entrepreneurship. These are the diversity of forms of ownership, directions of economic activity, independence and free movement in the methods of using earned funds. After gaining independence, the Uzbek people chose the path of conducting an economy based on market relations. The

organization of market relations is not such a simple task, but a very complex, responsible task that produces unexpected results, requires accurate calculation, ingenuity, courage, great moral courage from the head of the state, and makes a great historical turn in the life of the country.

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, who has assumed such responsibility, while developing a green economy based on market relations, paid attention to the issue of supporting the class of owners based on the expansion of property expropriation among the first of the tasks to be performed. In this regard, he said, "I will say it again and again, we will always support patriotic and selfless entrepreneurs who know how to do things, who create conditions for people to work and earn income..." [8]. Consequently, the nature of entrepreneurship requires social, economic and political stability in society.

In our opinion, entrepreneurship is the activity of a person preparing a project and decision on the basis of business, adopting it, developing laws and principles related to entrepreneurship, and purposefully influencing social and economic events and processes by means of business information exchange. Entrepreneurship, on the other hand, is constantly improving due to historical necessity. This has a positive effect on business activity. At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the activity in the field of entrepreneurship development is also recognized by our international community, "We have risen 7 places in the World Bank's "Doing Business" rating, ranked 8th among 190 countries of the world in terms of business registration, and are among the best reforming countries." Indicators such as [9] were a vivid expression of this.

References:

1. Ganiev B.S. Socio-economic and legal aspects of the development of entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Scientific bulletin. Scientific journal. / 2015. No. 4. - B. 49-52.
2. Mirziyoev Sh. New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2022. - B. 145.
3. Дудар Т.Е. Предпринимательство: культурфилософский и антропологический подход. Автореферат диссертации на соискание степени кандидата философских наук. - С-Петербург: 2005. - С. 10.
4. Amir Temur fertilizers. - Tashkent: Navroz, 1992. - B. 10-11.
5. Karimov I.A. There is no future without historical memory - Tashkent: Sharq, 1998. - B. 15.
6. Tokhliev N., Khakberdiev Q. and others. Basics of the economy of Uzbekistan - Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. - B. 146.

7. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Tashkent: Adolat, 2023. - B. 23-35.
8. Mirziyoev Sh. Our most important task is to create all the conditions for rapid and wider development of entrepreneurship. - Tashkent: Teacher, 2021. - B. 44.
9. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. - Tashkent: Image, 2020. - B. 8.

